

Redox reactive (RNC)Cu^{II} species stabilized in the solid state via halogen bond with I₂

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Abstract. The crystal structure of [Cu₂(μ-O)(μ-I)₂(CNXyl)₄]**2**·I₂ (**2**·I₂) was determined from single-crystal X-ray diffraction data. The adduct **2**·I₂ represents the first example of structurally characterized isocyanide-copper(II) complexes. In the structure of **2**·I₂, **2** forms independent chains connected through molecular iodine via I••I–I••I halogen bonding. The DFT calculations and topological analysis of the electron density distribution within the formalism of Bader's theory (QTAIM method) were performed for model complex **2**·I₂ and the obtained results allowed the attribution of these contacts to moderate strength (3.8–5.3 kcal/mol) non-covalent contacts exhibiting some covalent character.

Introduction

In the past decade the phenomenon of halogen bonding (XB) has attracted significant attention due to its important role in material design, molecular recognition, catalysis, and medicinal chemistry. This role is collaterally reflected in the appearance of many recent reviews^[1] and book^[2] devoted to XB. Among different XB donors, molecular iodine is known to form strong halogen bonds.^[2–3] Current studies relevant to XB involving I₂ are focused on catalysis of various organic reactions,^[4] and of material design utilizing XBs.^[5]

In continuation of our ongoing project on chemistry of isocyanide complexes, on the one hand,^[6] and XB involving metal complexes, on the other hand,^[7] we synthesized (RNC)Cu^I species^[6b] and planned to study their co-crystallization with various XB donors. For the system [CuBr(CNXyl)₃]–CHI₃ we obtained the unexpected [Cu₂(μ-O)(μ-I)₂(CNXyl)₄]**2** adduct and herein we report the structure of the (RNC)Cu^{II} complex, where the framework and potentially unstable oxidation state are stabilized by XB.

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Results and Discussion

The complex $[\text{CuBr}(\text{CNXyl})_3]$ (**1**)^[6b] was mixed with CHI_3 (1:1 molar ratio) in a MeOH solution and the mixture was left (at 50 °C) in an open vial under daylight. After 2d, a few crystals of $[\text{Cu}_2(\mu\text{-O})(\mu\text{-I})_2(\text{CNXyl})_4]\cdot\text{I}_2$ (**2**· I_2) were released and they were mechanically separated and studied by single crystal X-ray crystallography (SXRD). Although the mechanism of generation of **2**· I_2 is yet unknown, we believe most likely this adduct is formed via the reported^[8] light-induced and H_2O -assisted decomposition of CHI_3 to I_2 and I^- , followed by Br/I and CNXyl/I ligand exchange at the copper(I) center with subsequent oxidation of copper(I) by atmospheric O_2 . Alternatively, copper(I) could be oxidized with I_2 with subsequent coordination and deprotonation of H_2O , which is transformed to the O^{2-} -bridging ligand.

Fig. 1. View of the structure of **2**· I_2 adduct with the atomic numbering schemes, the $\text{I}\cdots\text{I}\cdots\text{I}$ contacts are given by dashed lines. Only one O1 position is represented.

In the **2**· I_2 , two Cu atoms are bridged through one O atom (chemical occupancy for this oxygen atom is $\frac{1}{2}$) and also by the two iodine atoms (**Figure 1**); the corresponding distances around the Cu center are usual.^[9] The Cu–Cu distance [2.9987(17) Å] is longer than the sum of Bondi's van der Waals (vdW) radii (2.80 Å)^[10] indicating the absence of the $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}\cdots\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}$ cuprophilic interactions, and this statement was confirmed by the theoretical calculations (see below). Parameters of the CNXyl ligands are comparable with those for the known isocyanide-copper(I) species,^[6b] while XRD structures of isocyanide-based copper(II) complexes are hitherto unreported. Thus, **2**· I_2 represents the first example of structurally characterized isocyanide-copper(II) complexes. The known copper(II) species bearing isocyanide ligands include $[\text{Cu}(\text{CNR})_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]\text{X}_2$ (R = Bu', $\text{C}(\text{Me})_2\text{CH}_2\text{CMe}_3$; X = ClO_4 , BF_4),^[11] and

[Cu(CN{Y}NC)₂X₂] (Y = CMe₂CH₂CH₂CMe₂, CH₂CH₂; X = ClO₄, BF₄, OTf),^[12] but the structures have not been supported by SXRD data. Redox potential values for Cu^{II}/Cu^I systems depend on ligand nature and it is expected that ligation of isocyanides, exhibiting rather strong π-acceptor properties, leads to stabilization of (RNC)Cu^I complexes. Indeed, isocyanide copper(I) species are much more abundant than copper(II) complexes. By contrast, herein we observe stabilization of (RNC)Cu^{II} in the crystalline state.

Complexes featuring the {Cu₂I₂O} core have been previously studied and their examples are represented by the neutral complexes [Cu₂I₂O(diamine)₂],^[13] XRD structures of which have not been studied. Similar complexes featuring C-donor ligands were unknown until this work.

Fig. 2. Packing of the halogen bonded chains in the co-crystal adduct (100) (upper). The Cu₂I₂O halogen bonded fragment (lower). Contacts shorter than the sum of Bondi's van der Waals radii are given by dashed lines.

In the structure of 2•I₂ (Figure 2), 2 forms independent chains connected through molecular iodine via I•••I–I•••I XB. Weak interactions between the coordinated iodine atom and I₂ are represented by type II halogen-halogen contact,^[14] where electrophilic region of the neutral iodine atom is interacting with the nucleophilic region of the Cu^{II}-bound bridged iodide. Two short contacts Cu–I•••I–I•••I–Cu [*d*(I•••I)] = 3.2780(7) Å are substantially less than Bondi's *R*_{vdw}(I) + *R*_{vdw}(I) = 3.96 Å separations,^[10] but *d*(I–I) = 2.7745(10) Å is slightly elongated than in molecular iodine (2.710 Å^[15]). The values of ∠(I–I•••I) (176.735(16)°) and ∠(I•••I–Cu) [105.93(3)°] angles allow the attribution of

the I•••I–I•••I contacts to type II halogen-halogen contacts, or in other words, to the real XB.^[14]

Contacts I•••I–I•••I are rather abundant and known for some associates of iodide complexes with I₂. More than 50 examples of these associates can be found upon analysis of CCDC (ConQuest v1.19) and I•••I distances in these species vary in the 3.24–3.86 Å range. The lengths of I•••I contact in 2•I₂ is close to the lower limit of this range. Similar relatively short distances for both I•••I contacts in the I•••I–I•••I moiety have been detected for [H₅O₂•crown]₂[Pd₂I₆]•I₂ (crown = dibenzo-24-crown-8; 3.3235(15) Å)^[16] and [RuI₂(CNBu^t)₄]•I₂ (3.3153(7) Å),^[17] and also for one of the two contacts I•••I–I•••I in [PdI{C₆H₃(CH₂NMe₂-2,6)}]•I₂ (the shortest I•••I separation is 3.2720(12) Å),^[18] [Ir₂Cp₂I₂(μ-I)₂]•I₂ (3.241(3) Å),^[19] [PtI₄(1,10-phen)]•I₂ (the shortest I•••I separation is 3.2878(4) Å),^[20] and [RuI₂(CO)₂(bpy)]•I₂ (the shortest I•••I separation is 3.255(1) Å).^[21] Noteworthy, 2•I₂ is the first documented example, where the bridged iodine ligands, I[−], are involved in the I•••I–I•••I contact. In 2•I₂ the π-stacking interactions between the Xyl rings of the adjacent complex molecules were also detected with the intermolecular contacts in the 3.4–3.7 Å range.

On the contrary, the I•••I–I•••I linkage could be considered as a bridging polyiodide dianion [I₄]^{2−}, where each terminal iodine atom is bound with two copper centers from the two different {Cu₂O} moieties thus forming the polymeric chains [Cu₂O(I₄)(CNXyl)₄]_n. Similarly, the [CuI₂(diap)]•½I₂ (diap = 2,6-diacetylpyridine dihydrazone) complex was considered^[22] as a dimeric species bearing a bridging polyiodide dianion [I₄]^{2−}. Recently polyhalides and polyhalide complexes attracted significant attention due to their important role in dye sensitized solar cells.^[23] This attention is reflected in growing number of recent publications in this area, *e.g.* experimental works devoted to polybromide^[24] and mixed polyiodo-bromide complexes,^[25] and other polyhalide metal complexes.^[23, 26] Noteworthy that structures with discrete dianions [I₄]^{2−} are also known and these linkages demonstrate the difference between the internal and external iodine•••iodine distances (2.76–2.85 vs. 3.17–3.55 Å).^[22] These distances are comparable with those observed in 2•I₂ (2.77 vs. 3.28 Å) and in [CuI₂(diap)]•½I₂ (2.81 vs. 3.35 Å).^[27] Based on these considerations, 2•I₂ alternatively could be taken as a polyhalide complex.

In order to ~~confirm~~ support or disprove the hypothesis on the existence of these non-covalent interactions in the solid state and to quantify their energies, we carried out the Hirshfeld surface analysis for the crystal structure of 2•I₂ and performed DFT calculations followed by the topological analysis of the electron density distribution within the framework of Bader's theory (QTAIM method)^[28] for the supramolecular cluster 2•I₂ taken as model. This approach has already been successfully used by us upon studies of different non-covalent interactions in various transition metal complexes.^[7, 29]

The molecular Hirshfeld surface represents an area where molecules come into contacts, and its analysis gives the possibility of an additional insight into the nature of intermolecular interactions in the crystalline state. We

carried out the Hirshfeld surface analysis for the X-ray structure of $2 \cdot \text{I}_2$ to understand what kind of intermolecular contacts gives the largest contributions in the crystal packing.

Fig. 3. Hirshfeld molecular surface for the X-ray structure of $2 \cdot \text{I}_2$.

For the visualization, mapping of the normalized contact distance (d_{norm}) was used; its negative value enables identification of molecular regions of substantial importance for detection of short contacts. **Figure 3** depicts the Hirshfeld molecular surface for the X-ray structure of $2 \cdot \text{I}_2$. In this Hirshfeld molecular surface, the regions of shortest intermolecular contacts are visualized by red circle areas. The main partial contributions of different intermolecular contacts to the molecular Hirshfeld surface are H–H 38.2%, C–H 30.4%, I–H 17.3%, N–H 4.8%, O–H 1.7%, C–C 1.6%, I–C 1.5%, I–I 1.3%, and I–O 1.1% (for appropriate Hirshfeld surface fingerprint plots see **Figure S1** in Supporting Information). The contributions of all other intermolecular contacts do not exceed 1%. Thus, the Hirshfeld surface analysis for the obtained X-ray structure of $2 \cdot \text{I}_2$ reveals that crystal packing is determined primarily by intermolecular contacts involving hydrogen atoms (H–H, C–H, I–H, and N–H).

However, the Hirshfeld surface analysis does not answer the question on energies of these contacts and, therefore, the DFT calculations and QTAIM analysis should be further performed to study the nature of the non-covalent interaction, discussed above, more deeply. The results of QTAIM analysis are summarized in **Table 1**. The Poincaré–Hopf relationship was satisfied, and all critical points were found. The contour line diagram of the Laplacian distribution $\nabla^2\rho(\mathbf{r})$, bond paths, and selected zero-flux surfaces for the Cu–I \cdots I–I XBs in the model supramolecular cluster $2 \cdot \text{I}_2$ as well as atomic basins of electron density gradient lines map are shown in **Figure S2** in Supporting Information. To visualize studied non-covalent interactions, reduced density gradient (RDG) analysis^[30] was carried out, and RDG isosurface was plotted (**Figure S2** in Supporting Information).

Table 1. Values of the density of all electrons – $\rho(\mathbf{r})$, Laplacian of electron density – $\nabla^2\rho(\mathbf{r})$, energy density – H_b , potential energy density – $V(\mathbf{r})$, and Lagrangian kinetic energy – $G(\mathbf{r})$ (Hartree) at the bond critical points (3, –1), corresponding to the Cu–I \cdots I–I XBs in the model supramolecular cluster $2 \cdot \text{I}_2$, as well as energies for these contacts E_{int} (kcal/mol), defined by two approaches.

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Contact	$\rho(\mathbf{r})$	$\nabla^2\rho(\mathbf{r})$	H_b	$V(\mathbf{r})$	$G(\mathbf{r})$	E_{int}^a	E_{int}^b
Cu-I...I-I (a)	0.027	0.042	-0.003	-0.016	0.014	5.0	3.8
Cu-I...I-I (b)	0.026	0.046	-0.003	-0.017	0.014	5.3	3.8

$$^a E_{int} = -V(\mathbf{r})/2^{[31]}$$

$$^b E_{int} = 0.429G(\mathbf{r})^{[32]}$$

The QTAIM analysis demonstrates presence of appropriate bond critical points (BCPs) (3, -1) for the Cu-I...I-I...I-Cu non-covalent interactions in the model supramolecular cluster $2 \cdot I_2$, and does not reveal any BCPs for the cuprophilic interactions $Cu^{II} \cdots Cu^{II}$. Energy for these contacts was defined according to the procedures proposed by Espinosa *et al.*^[31] and Vener *et al.*^[32] (**Table 1**), and one can state that these non-covalent interactions are of moderate strength (3.8–5.3 kcal/mol), and their energy is comparable with similar Ru-I...I-I...I-Ru non-covalent interactions in crystals of $[RuI_2(CO)_2(bpy)] \cdot I_2$ (4.1–4.7 kcal/mol)^[21]. The I...I contacts in $2 \cdot I_2$ correspond to intermediate covalent/non-covalent type of interatomic interactions with the negative value of electron energy density and positive Laplacian value. Noticeable values of the Wiberg bond indices (*viz.* 0.21–0.24) for the appropriate contacts I...I, computed by using the natural bond orbital (NBO) partitioning scheme,^[33] additionally confirm this observation. Note that computed values of the Wiberg bond indices for similar types of interatomic Br...Br interactions in crystals of 2-bromopyridinium salt of the one-dimensional polymeris $(2-BrPyH)_2[BiBr_5]$ (*viz.* 0.04)^[34] and $(cation)_2\{[TeBr_6](Br_2)\}$ (*viz.* 0.09)^[25b] are significantly lower. The NBO analysis revealed intermolecular charge transfer from the $\mu-I^-$ ligand to I_2 in $2 \cdot I_2$. The second-order perturbation theory analysis indicates that this intermolecular charge transfer is mainly associated with the transitions from lone pairs of the $\mu-I^-$ ligand to 2-center anti-bond orbitals of I_2 and total $E(2)$ is 18.93 kcal/mol.

Conclusions

Adduct $[Cu_2(\mu-O)(\mu-I)_2(CNXy)_4] \cdot I_2$ ($2 \cdot I_2$) was successfully isolated in the crystalline state and characterized by SXRD, representing the first example of structurally characterized isocyanide copper(II) species. The structure of $2 \cdot I_2$ adduct is defined by I...I-I...I XB that participate in formation of independent chains of **2** and I_2 . Based on theoretical calculations data, these interactions are of moderate strength (3.8–5.3 kcal/mol) non-covalent contacts and exhibit some covalent character.

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Experimental section

Materials. Iodoform and solvents were obtained from commercial source and used as received. The copper(I) [CuBr(CNXY)₃] complex was synthesized ~~in~~ according to ~~with~~ the published method.^[6b]

X-ray structure determinations. Crystal of **2**·I₂ was measured on an Agilent Technologies SuperNova diffractometer at 100K using monochromated CuK α radiation. The structure has been solved by the direct methods by means of the SHELX program^[35] incorporated in the OLEX2 program package.^[36] For crystallographic data and refinement parameters see Supplementary material (Table S1). The carbon-bound H atoms were placed in calculated positions and were included in the refinement in the ‘riding’ model approximation, with U_{iso}(H) set to 1.5U_{eq}(C) and C–H 0.98 Å for CH₃ groups, with U_{iso}(H) set to 1.2U_{eq}(C) and C–H 0.99 Å for CH₂ groups and with U_{iso}(H) set to 1.2U_{eq}(C), C–H 0.95 Å for CH groups. Empirical absorption correction was applied in CrysAlisPro^[37] program complex using spherical harmonics, implemented in SCALE3 ABSPACK scaling algorithm. Supplementary crystallographic data for this paper have been deposited at Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre (CCDC 1577281) and can be obtained free of charge via www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk/data_request/cif.

Computational details. The single point calculations based on the experimental X-ray geometry (crystallographic coordinates; the positions of H atoms were not optimized; the C–H_{Ph} and C–H_{Me} distances are 0.93 Å and 0.96 Å, respectively) have been carried out at the DFT level of theory using the M06 functional^[38] (this functional was specifically developed to describe weak dispersion forces and non-covalent interactions) with the help of Gaussian-09 program package.^[39] The Douglas–Kroll–Hess 2nd order scalar relativistic calculations requested relativistic core Hamiltonian were carried out using DZP-DKH basis sets^[40] for all atoms. The topological analysis of the electron density distribution with the help of the atoms in molecules (QTAIM) method developed by Bader^[28] has been performed by using the Multiwfn program (version 3.3.8).^[41] The Cartesian atomic coordinates for the model supramolecular cluster **2**·I₂ are presented in **Table S2** (Supporting Information). The Hirshfeld molecular surface was generated by CrystalExplorer 3.1 program^[42] based on the results of the X-ray study. The normalized contact distances, d_{norm},^[43] based on Bondi’s van der Waals radii,^[10] were mapped into the Hirshfeld molecular surface. In the color scale, negative values of d_{norm} are visualized by the red color indicating contacts shorter than the sum of van der Waals radii. The white color denotes intermolecular distances close to van der Waals contacts with d_{norm} equal to zero. In turn, contacts longer than the sum of van der Waals radii with positive d_{norm} values are colored with blue.

Supporting information

Crystal data, Cartesian atomic coordinates, and Hirshfeld surface fingerprint plots.

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References

- [1] a) M. H. Kolář, P. Hobza, Computer Modeling of Halogen Bonds and Other σ -Hole Interactions, *Chem. Rev.* **2016**, *116*, 5155-5187; b) G. Cavallo, P. Metrangolo, R. Milani, T. Pilati, A. Priimagi, G. Resnati, G. Terraneo, The Halogen Bond, *Chem. Rev.* **2016**, *116*, 2478-2601; c) V. Oliveira, E. Kraka, D. Cremer, Quantitative Assessment of Halogen Bonding Utilizing Vibrational Spectroscopy, *Inorg. Chem.* **2017**, *56*, 488-502; d) F. Meyer, P. Dubois, Halogen bonding at work: recent applications in synthetic chemistry and materials science, *CrystEngComm* **2013**, *15*, 3058-3071.
- [2] *Halogen Bonding: Fundamentals and Applications, Vol. 126*, Springer Berlin Heidelberg, **2008**.
- [3] O. Hassel, C. Rømming, T. Tufte, Crystal Structure of the 1:1 Addition Compound Formed by 4-Picoline and Iodine, *Acta Chem. Scand.* **1961**, *15*, 967-974.
- [4] a) M. Breugst, E. Detmar, D. von der Heiden, Origin of the Catalytic Effects of Molecular Iodine: A Computational Analysis, *ACS Catal.* **2016**, *6*, 3203-3212; b) D. von der Heiden, S. Bozkus, M. Klussmann, M. Breugst, Reaction Mechanism of Iodine-Catalyzed Michael Additions, *J. Org. Chem.* **2017**, *82*, 4037-4043; c) M. Breugst, D. von der Heiden, J. Schmauck, Novel Noncovalent Interactions in Catalysis: A Focus on Halogen, Chalcogen, and Anion- π Bonding, *Synthesis* **2017**, *49*, 3224-3236.
- [5] a) J.-X. Lin, J. Liang, J.-F. Feng, B. Karadeniz, J. Lu, R. Cao, Iodine uptake and enhanced electrical conductivity in a porous coordination polymer based on cucurbit[6]uril, *Inorg. Chem. Frontiers* **2016**, *3*, 1393-1397; b) L. J. McAllister, C. Prasang, J. P. W. Wong, R. J. Thatcher, A. C. Whitwood, B. Donnio, P. O'Brien, P. B. Karadakov, D. W. Bruce, Halogen-bonded liquid crystals of 4-alkoxystilbazoles with molecular iodine: a very short halogen bond and unusual mesophase stability, *Chem. Commun.* **2013**, *49*, 3946-3948.
- [6] a) V. P. Boyarskiy, N. A. Bokach, K. V. Luzyanin, V. Y. Kukushkin, Metal-Mediated and Metal-Catalyzed Reactions of Isocyanides, *Chem. Rev.* **2015**, *115*, 2698-2779; b) A. A. Melekhova, A. S. Novikov, K. V. Luzyanin, N. A. Bokach, G. L. Starova, V. V. Gurzhiy, V. Y. Kukushkin, Tris-isocyanide copper(I) complexes: Synthetic, structural, and theoretical study, *Inorg. Chim. Acta* **2015**, *434*, 31-36.
- [7] D. M. Ivanov, A. S. Novikov, I. V. Ananyev, Y. V. Kirina, V. Y. Kukushkin, Halogen bonding between metal centers and halocarbons, *Chem. Commun.* **2016**, *52*, 5565-5568.
- [8] a) Y. Xiao, R. Fan, L. Zhang, J. Yue, R. D. Webster, T.-T. Lim, Photodegradation of iodinated trihalomethanes in aqueous solution by UV 254 irradiation, *Water Research* **2014**,

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- 49, 275-285; b) E. Kremers, E. C. W. Koske, Decomposition of iodoform at the light. *Pharm. Arch.* **1998**, *1*, 194-200.
- [9] A. G. Orpen, L. Brammer, F. H. Allen, O. Kennard, D. G. Watson, R. Taylor, Supplement. Tables of bond lengths determined by X-ray and neutron diffraction. Part 2. Organometallic compounds and co-ordination complexes of the d- and f-block metals, *J. Chem. Soc. Dalton Trans.* **1989**, S1-S83.
- [10] A. Bondi, van der Waals Volumes and Radii of Metals in Covalent Compounds, *J. Phys. Chem.* **1966**, *70*, 3006-3007.
- [11] R. W. Stephany, W. Drenth, Copper(II) alkyl isocyanide complexes, *Recl. Trav. Chim. Pays-Bas* **1970**, *89*, 305-312.
- [12] M. Dartiguenave, Y. Dartiguenave, A. Guitard, A. Mari, A. L. Beauchamp, Synthesis and characterization of copper, manganese and zinc complexes of the bidentate diisocyanide ligands 2,5-dimethyl 2,5-diisocyanohexane (TMB) and 1,2-diisocyanooethane (DHB), *Polyhedron* **1989**, *8*, 317-323.
- [13] M. A. El-Sayed, G. Davies, T. S. Kasem, Products and kinetics of the oxidation of neutral dimeric iodo(N,N,N',N'-tetraalkyl diamine)copper(I) complexes [LCuI]₂ by dioxygen in nitrobenzene, *Inorg. Chem.* **1990**, *29*, 4730-4735.
- [14] P. Metrangolo, G. Resnati, Type II halogen...halogen contacts are halogen bonds, *IUCrJ* **2014**, *1*, 5-7.
- [15] F. Bertolotti, A. V. Shishkina, A. Forni, G. Gervasio, A. I. Stash, V. G. Tsirelson, Intermolecular Bonding Features in Solid Iodine, *Cryst. Growth Design* **2014**, *14*, 3587-3595.
- [16] C. Walbaum, I. Pantenburg, G. Meyer, Molecular iodine catenation in the anionic chains [Pd₂I₆(I₂)₂]⁻, *Cryst. Research Technol.* **2008**, *43*, 1183-1186.
- [17] M. E. G. Mosquera, P. Gomez-Sal, I. Diaz, L. M. Aguirre, A. Ienco, G. Manca, C. Mealli, Intriguing I₂ Reduction in the Iodide for Chloride Ligand Substitution at a Ru(II) Complex: Role of Mixed Trihalides in the Redox Mechanism, *Inorg. Chem.* **2016**, *55*, 283-291.
- [18] A. Mills, M. A. M. van Beek, G. van Koten, A. L. Spek, [2,6-Bis[(dimethylamino-kappaN)methyl]phenyl-kappaC]iodopalladium(II) bis(diiodine), *Acta Cryst. Sect. C* **2002**, *58*, 304-306.
- [19] A. Millan, P. M. Bailey, P. M. Maitlis, Pentamethylcyclopentadienyl-rhodium and -iridium complexes. Part 34. Preparation and X-ray structure of the polyiodo-compound [Ir(C₅Me₅)₂I₆] and related species, *J. Chem. Soc. Dalton Trans.* **1982**, 73-77.
- [20] K. D. Buse, H. J. Keller, H. Pritzkow, Reaction of molecular iodine with cis-dihalo(2,2'-bipyridyl)platinum(II) and cis-dihalo(1,10-phenanthroline)platinum(II). Oxidative addition and inclusion compounds, *Inorg. Chem.* **1977**, *16*, 1072-1076.
- [21] X. Ding, M. J. Tuikka, P. Hirva, V. Y. Kukushkin, A. S. Novikov, M. Haukka, Fine-tuning halogen bonding properties of diiodine through halogen-halogen charge transfer - extended [Ru(2,2[prime or minute]-bipyridine)(CO)₂X₂]₂•I₂ systems (X = Cl, Br, I), *CrystEngComm* **2016**, *18*, 1987-1995.
- [22] M. F. Belicci, G. G. Fava, C. Pelizzi, I₄²⁻ Ions in the Structure of (2,6-Diacetylpyridine dihydrazone)diiodocopper(II)•1/2I₂, *Acta Cryst.* **1981**, B37, 924-926.
- [23] H. Haller, S. Riedel, Recent Discoveries of Polyhalogen Anions – from Bromine to Fluorine, *Z. Anorg. Allg. Chem.* **2014**, *640*, 1281-1291.
- [24] a) L. Botana, J. Ruiz, J.M. Seco, A.J. Mota, A. Rodrigues-Dieguez, R. Sillanpaa, E. Colacio, Influence of the anions on the structure and magnetic properties of a series of bis(μ-diphenoxo)-bridged linear trinuclear copper(II) complexes: an experimental and theoretical study, *Dalton Trans.*, **2011**, *40*, 12462-12471; b) M. Carla Aragoni, M. Arca, S.L. Coles, F.A. Devillanova, H.B. Hursthouse, F. Isaia, V. Lippolis, Reactivity of phosphonodithioato-dpdt NiII mixed ligand complexes with halogens: first example of a metal-coordinating tribromide anion, *Dalton Trans.*, **2012**, *41*, 6611-6613; c) A.

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Bulatova_MS_R
edox reactive
(RNC)Cu_2018

Date
12.09.2022

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9 (11)

- Okrut, C. Feldmann, $\{[P(o\text{-tolyl})_3]Br\}_2[Cu_2Br_6](Br_2)$ —An Ionic Compound Containing Molecular Bromine, *Inorg. Chem.* **2008**, *47*, 3084–3087; d) S.A. Adonin, I.D. Gorokh, P.A. Abramov, P.E. Plyusnin, M.N. Sokolov, V.P. Fedin, Trapping molecular bromine: a one-dimensional bromobismuthate complex with Br_2 as a linker, *Dalton Trans.* **2016**, *45*, 3691–3693; e) S.A. Adonin, I.D. Gorokh, D.G. Samsonenko, M.N. Sokolov, V.P. Fedin, Bi(III) polybromides: a new chapter in coordination chemistry of bismuth, *Chem. Commun.*, **2016**, *52*, 5061–5063; f) D. Hausmann, C. Feldmann, Bromine-rich Zinc Bromides: $Zn_6Br_{12}(18\text{-crown-6})_2 \times (Br_2)_5$, $Zn_4Br_8(18\text{-crown-6})_2 \times (Br_2)_3$, and $Zn_6Br_{12}(18\text{-crown-6})_2 \times (Br_2)_2$, *Inorg. Chem.* **2016**, *55*, 6141–6147; g) S.A. Adonin, D.S. Perekalin, I.D. Gorokh, D.G. Samsonenko, M.N. Sokolov, V.P. Fedin, Heterogeneous bromination of alkenes using Bi(III) polybromide complexes as $\{Br_2\}$ source, *RSC Adv.* **2016**, *6*, 62011–62013;
- [25] a) V.Yu. Kotov, N.P. Simonenko, A.B. Ilyukhin, Hybrid halobismuthates: a coordinated $BrIBr^-$ anion, *Mendeleev Commun.* **2017**, *27*, 454–455; b) A.N. Usoltsev, S.A. Adonin, A.S. Novikov, D.G. Samsonenko, M.N. Sokolov, V.P. Fedin, One-dimensional polymeric polybromotellurates(IV): structural and theoretical insights into halogen...halogen contacts, *CrystEngComm*, **2017**, *19*, 5934–5939;
- [26] M.E.G. Mosquera, I. Egido, C. Hortelano, M. Lopez-Lopez, P. Gomez-Sal, Comparison of Halogen Bonding Networks With Ru(II) Complexes and Analysis of the Influence of the XB Interactions on Their Reactivity, *Faraday Discuss.*, **2017**, *203*, 257–283.
- [27] M. Węclawik, A. Gaęor, A. Piecha, R. Jakubas, W. Medycki, Synthesis, crystal structure and phase transitions of a series of imidazolium iodides, *CrystEngComm*, **2013**, *15*, 5633–5640.
- [28] R. F. W. Bader, A quantum theory of molecular structure and its applications, *Chem. Rev.* **1991**, *91*, 893–928.
- [29] a) D. M. Ivanov, A. S. Novikov, G. L. Starova, M. Haukka, V. Y. Kukushkin, A family of heterotetrameric clusters of chloride species and halomethanes held by two halogen and two hydrogen bonds, *CrystEngComm* **2016**, *18*, 5278–5286; b) T. V. Serebryanskaya, A. S. Novikov, P. V. Gushchin, M. Haukka, R. E. Asfin, P. M. Tolstoy, V. Y. Kukushkin, Identification and H(D)-bond energies of C-H(D)[three dots, centered]Cl interactions in chloride-haloalkane clusters: a combined X-ray crystallographic, spectroscopic, and theoretical study, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.* **2016**, *18*, 14104–14112; c) K. I. Kulish, A. S. Novikov, P. M. Tolstoy, D. S. Bolotin, N. A. Bokach, A. A. Zolotarev, V. Y. Kukushkin, Solid state and dynamic solution structures of O-carbamidine amidoximes gives further insight into the mechanism of zinc(II)-mediated generation of 1,2,4-oxadiazoles, *J. Mol. Struct.* **2016**, *1111*, 142–150; d) D. M. Ivanov, Y. V. Kirina, A. S. Novikov, G. L. Starova, V. Y. Kukushkin, Efficient π -stacking with benzene provides 2D assembly of trans-[PtCl₂(p-CF₃C₆H₄CN)₂], *J. Mol. Struct.* **2016**, *1104*, 19–23; e) A. S. Mikherdov, M. A. Kinzhalov, A. S. Novikov, V. P. Boyarskiy, I. A. Boyarskaya, D. V. Dar'in, G. L. Starova, V. Y. Kukushkin, Difference in Energy between Two Distinct Types of Chalcogen Bonds Drives Regioisomerization of Binuclear (Diaminocarbene)PdII Complexes, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2016**, *138*, 14129–14137.
- [30] E. R. Johnson, S. Keinan, P. Mori-Sánchez, J. Contreras-García, A. J. Cohen, W. Yang, Revealing Noncovalent Interactions, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2010**, *132*, 6498–6506.
- [31] E. Espinosa, E. Molins, C. Lecomte, Hydrogen bond strengths revealed by topological analyses of experimentally observed electron densities, *Chem. Phys. Lett.* **1998**, *285*, 170–173.

Author	Title	File Name	Date	Page
Margarita Bulatova, † Anna A. Melekhova, † Alexander S. Novikov, † Daniil M. Ivanov, † Nadezhda A. Bokach, †*	Redox reactive (RNC)Cu^{II} species stabilized in the solid state via halogen bond with I₂	Bulatova_MS_R edox reactive (RNC)Cu_2018	12.09.2022	10 (11)

- [32] M. V. Vener, A. N. Egorova, A. V. Churakov, V. G. Tsirelson, Intermolecular hydrogen bond energies in crystals evaluated using electron density properties: DFT computations with periodic boundary conditions, *J. Comput. Chem.* **2012**, *33*, 2303-2309.
- [33] E. D. Glendening, C. R. Landis, F. Weinhold, Natural bond orbital methods, *Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Computational Molecular Science* **2012**, *2*, 1-42.
- [34] S. A. Adonin,[†] I. D. Gorokh,[†] A. S. Novikov,[†] P. A. Abramov,[†] M. N. Sokolov,[†] V. P. Fedin, Halogen Contacts-Induced Unusual Coloring in Bi^{III} Bromide Complex: Anion-to-Cation Charge Transfer via Br•••Br Interactions, *Chem.–Eur. J.*, **2017**, *23*, 15612–15616.
- [35] G. M. Sheldrick, A short history of SHELX, *Acta Cryst.* **2008**, *A64*, 112-122.
- [36] O. V. Dolomanov, L. J. Bourhis, R. J. Gildea, J. A. K. Howard, H. Puschmann, OLEX2: A complete structure solution, refinement and analysis program, *J. Appl. Cryst.* **2009**, *42*, 339-341.
- [37] CrysAlisPro. Agilent Technologies. Version 1.171.36.20 (release 27-06-2012).
- [38] Y. Zhao, D. G. Truhlar, The M06 suite of density functionals for main group thermochemistry, thermochemical kinetics, noncovalent interactions, excited states, and transition elements: two new functionals and systematic testing of four M06-class functionals and 12 other functionals, *Theor. Chem. Acc.* **2008**, *120*, 215-241.
- [39] M. J. Frisch, G. W. Trucks, H. B. Schlegel, G. E. Scuseria, M. A. Robb, J. R. Cheeseman, G. Scalmani, V. Barone, B. Mennucci, G. A. Petersson, H. Nakatsuji, M. Caricato, X. Li, H. P. Hratchian, A. F. Izmaylov, J. Bloino, G. Zheng, J. L. Sonnenberg, M. Hada, M. Ehara, K. Toyota, R. Fukuda, J. Hasegawa, M. Ishida, T. Nakajima, Y. Honda, O. Kitao, H. Nakai, T. Vreven, J. A. Montgomery, Jr., J. E. Peralta, F. Ogliaro, M. Bearpark, J. J. Heyd, E. Brothers, K. N. Kudin, V. N. Staroverov, R. Kobayashi, J. Normand, K. Raghavachari, A. Rendell, J. C. Burant, S. S. Iyengar, J. Tomasi, M. Cossi, N. Rega, J. M. Millam, M. Klene, J. E. Knox, J. B. Cross, V. Bakken, C. Adamo, J. Jaramillo, R. Gomperts, R. E. Stratmann, O. Yazyev, A. J. Austin, R. Cammi, C. Pomelli, J. W. Ochterski, R. L. Martin, K. Morokuma, V. G. Zakrzewski, G. A. Voth, P. Salvador, J. J. Dannenberg, S. Dapprich, A. D. Daniels, O. Farkas, J. B. Foresman, J. V. Ortiz, J. Cioslowski, and D. J. Fox, *Gaussian 09*, Revision A.01, Gaussian, Inc.: Wallingford, CT, **2009**.
- [40] a) F. E. Jorge, A. C. Neto, G. G. Camiletti, S. F. Machado, Contracted Gaussian basis sets for Douglas–Kroll–Hess calculations: Estimating scalar relativistic effects of some atomic and molecular properties, *J. Chem. Phys.* **2009**, *130*, 064108; b) R. C. de Berrêdo, F. E. Jorge, All-electron double zeta basis sets for platinum: Estimating scalar relativistic effects on platinum(II) anticancer drugs, *J. Mol. Struct. THEOCHEM* **2010**, *961*, 107-112; c) C. L. Barros, P. J. P. de Oliveira, F. E. Jorge, A. Canal Neto, M. Campos, Gaussian basis set of double zeta quality for atoms Rb through Xe: application in non-relativistic and relativistic calculations of atomic and molecular properties, *Mol. Phys.* **2010**, *108*, 1965-1972.
- [41] T. Lu, F. Chen, Multiwfn: A multifunctional wavefunction analyzer, *J. Comput. Chem.* **2012**, *33*, 580-592.
- [42] a) S. K. Wolff, D. J. Grimwood, J. J. McKinnon, M. J. Turner, D. Jayatilaka, M. A. Spackman, *Vol. Version 3.1*, University of Western Australia, **2012**; b) M. A. Spackman, D. Jayatilaka, Hirshfeld surface analysis, *CrystEngComm* **2009**, *11*, 19-32.
- [43] J. J. McKinnon, D. Jayatilaka, M. A. Spackman, Towards quantitative analysis of intermolecular interactions with Hirshfeld surfaces, *Chem. Commun.* **2007**, 3814-3816.

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